

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Klein**FIRST NAME:** Angela**PROGRAM CODE:** DIRD**COURSE CODE :** ACA- 401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Cleenewerck

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied X US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author X did use Zotero to insert references

The author {Citation}X did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

EVEN IF NOTHING IS NEW

INTRODUCTION

I have been an English language learner for my whole life, have taught children to read and to write for the past 22 years, have completed my master's, and have even taught courses in academic paper writing to Roman Catholic deacon candidates at the beginning of their formation programs. I am always amazed by the little things that can change your perspective or take you out of your comfort zone when learning new skills, applications or designs. For me, some of these new learnings have taken the task of writing this response paper to new complicated levels while the comfort of known learnings has brought me closer to my comfort zone.

1) ACADEMIC WRITING

I have been teaching the process of essay writing to children and adults for years and I know to focus on teaching the same main points every time: research, formulate a thesis, make a plan, write, cite, edit – all in no particular order because paper writing is “not a linear process” (EUCLID 2015, 1). The process of writing needs a roadmap of traffic circles, U-turns, and pit stops in order to get to the end goal of a well written paper. There are times when the research is the difficult part of writing and other times when the organization of the paper is more difficult. Every paper needs a different amount of time spent on a different part of the writing process. “An academic paper aims to persuade the reader of an idea based on evidence” and a well-planned, well researched, well designed paper will do just that (EUCLID 2015, 1).

2) THESIS

The thesis is the design center of any paper and it is important to constantly be checking to be sure that everything you write is related directly to your thesis – whether in support or in opposition. I like to think of the thesis as ‘my truth’ and my job, as I am writing, is to prove that my truth can be justified and supported. It is important to show different and opposing theories and perspectives because it shows that you have considered alternatives. Your plan, structure and research should support your thesis and follow it from your introduction paragraph to your closing paragraph.

3) CITATIONS/WORKS CITED

It is always important to cite sources – anytime you use another person’s ideas or words. “All academic essays MUST contain references. Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offence” (EUCLID 2015, 5). EUCLID, and this course, have introduced me to Zotero. I have not decided if this is good for me, or not...and so I introduce you to my first complication: technology. The first thing that I did before beginning period one was to watch the video (<https://vimeo.com/231577694>) on how to download Zotero and how to use it to compile and organize citations. It seemed easy enough. Needless to say, my Chromebook does not have Microsoft Word, so the plug in does not work and the lack of a hard drive makes compiling difficult; my laptop has an older version of Windows and so is also not compatible. I was left with my Mac desktop, which I hoped would make an easier job of everything. Luckily, after some frustration with my Chromebook and my laptop, I was able to download successfully to the Mac. I will have to gradually merge my knowledge of referencing when learning how to use Zotero. I am looking forward to using a tool that can help with the task of managing citations.

4) US VERSUS UK?

“Choose US or UK spelling (and punctuation) and be consistent” (EUCLID 2015, 7)! The choice to use US versus UK standards for citing, punctuation and for spelling, may be the most difficult thing for me to remain consistent with. As a Canadian, our rules of spelling follow the UK spellings, for example: colour, potatoe, centre, but as I was reading through the coursepack, I came to realize that our standards for word usage tend to follow the US style, for example: the use of have and had (EUCLID 2015, 56). I think that I am an example of when a style guide would come in handy. “A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2015, 52). Reading and rereading my work will be an important part of my editing, checking and rechecking for punctuation and spelling inconsistencies. I understand that I will have to focus on this part of my writing and to refer often to a style guide to remain consistent in my written work.

5) **THE USE OF THE PERSONAL PRONOUN 'I'**

It is true. I was told, and I often tell elementary students “not to use the first person singular” (EUCLID 2015, 44). We want children to differentiate between formal writing and journal writing, which is common in elementary schools. But it is important to remember that voice can be used to focus the points of an argument, and the use of “I” definitely indicates that the voice of the writer, and the writer’s point of view, are heard.

6) **CONCLUSION**

It really does not matter what I know. What will be most important is what I do not know or am not sure of. When it comes to formatting, researching and planning my papers, I should be good. On the other hand, I am going to have to be very careful to remain consistent in the areas of spelling, punctuation and word usage. Also, I hope that as this course progresses, I will become more comfortable using Zotero and that it will be an asset to me throughout this program.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401D Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed October 12, 2019).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.